

The Socio-Economic Essence of Efficiency and a Scientific Approach to It

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Abstract: *The article summarizes the theoretical essence of the efficiency category, presents the views of economists within the framework of defining the essential features of this category, provides a critical author's assessment of the views of economists and introduces the author's definition of the efficiency category. The quantitative and qualitative aspects of effectiveness are highlighted. Proposals are given to ensure the efficiency of economic entities.*

Keywords: *effectiveness, efficiency, results, quantitative results, qualitative results, resources, financial resource, income, profit, costs.*

In the context of innovative development of enterprise activities, the grounds for a real understanding of the theory of efficiency have matured, especially with the development of financial relations, which are built on the principle of financial sufficiency of enterprise activities. Therefore, any activity is considered from the standpoint of its efficiency. Efficiency as an economic category requires scientific understanding. This determines the need to consider it from the point of view of economic theory. It guides enterprises on the path to achieving a synergetic level of efficiency in dynamics, on identifying financial reserves for further improvement of the economic activities of enterprises based on the implementation of innovation achievements, modern technology and improved production organization [24]. Consequently, taking into account the above, it can be summarized that increasing the efficiency of an enterprise is an important factor in the implementation of synergetic goals of its activities, which is why the economic category of "efficiency" is so relevant at all stages of society's development.

In the process of studying economic, educational and periodical literature of the pre-transition period to a market economy, i.e. the 1970s-1990s, some shortcomings and problems were identified that are directly related to the definition of efficiency as an economic category, one of which is the authors' disjointed understanding of this concept and the lack of a clear definition of it as an economic category.

Therefore, the purpose of this scientific work is to generalize and rethink the approaches to the category of "efficiency" of economists in the conditions of the pre-transitional stage of economic development and after the establishment of the development of financial and economic relations.

In the pre-transition stage to the market, the issue of the efficiency of enterprise activity in one aspect or another was the subject of works by both domestic and foreign economists, such as L.I. Lopatnikov, and others.

In the economic dictionary of definitions, the category "efficiency" is given as an economic category only to generalize the economic meaning of efficiency, equating efficiency to the greatest degree of achieving a goal, realizing a potential opportunity through the ratio of costs to results. "Efficiency" is also considered from a different position and is characterized as a category conditioned by the costs of living and embodied labor necessary to change the quantitative and qualitative states of objects or natural processes in order to give them properties capable of satisfying social needs inherent in any production process. Considering the quantitative value of the efficiency indicator, the author of this view defines it as the ratio of final results to total costs (in labor or cost estimates).

Yes, at first glance, when defining the essence of efficiency as an economic category, we proceed from the fact that it reflects the achievement of the greatest socio-economic results at the lowest cost.

Indeed, efficiency is an economic category that reflects the most rational use of all available and potential production resources both at a separate enterprise and in the national economy as a whole, for maximum satisfaction of social needs with the least expenditure of social labor. From here, economists can single out the social aspect of efficiency, which is characteristic of the definitions of this category of authors of the pre-transition period.

Concerning the economists of this period, it should be noted that "efficiency" as an economic category and as a broad concept includes the most rational use of resources of all types, primarily financial, without which the activity of enterprises does not appear, in the interests of an increasingly complete satisfaction of the aggregate needs of the population. We note the socio-economic focus in determining efficiency, as well as the method of calculating efficiency by comparing results with costs (expenses).

Therefore, it is difficult to agree with the opinion of a number of economists, for example, V.K. Zadorozhny. In his opinion, efficiency is a concept that characterizes the ratio of the effect obtained as a result of economic activity to costs [6]. For some reason, this author overlooks the category of "effect" itself and does not note how this term is defined. And moving away from the category of effect, strengthening the opinion about efficiency in the context of this term, he notes that efficiency consists in the fact that the costs of labor, materials and other resources must ensure a return or give a result.

As a result of the analysis of approaches to defining the "efficiency" of pre-transition economists, a number of conclusions can be drawn. Among the approaches to There is no single, most meaningful definition of "efficiency" that would comprehensively reveal the essence of this category. In some cases, efficiency was considered as an abstract concept. Without a clear formulation of the category, programs were developed and proposed to improve the efficiency of a particular activity. Most authors agree, speaking about the methodology for calculating efficiency as the ratio of the effect to the costs (resources) that led to this effect. It is also worth noting some specific features in the definition of the declared category, characteristic of the economy of the transition period. The concept of "efficiency" in the literature of this period was considered mainly in the context of social production and increased productivity, often these definitions were and are still cited as unambiguous concepts. And also giving significant attention to social criteria when considering the category of "efficiency". Most of the works of economists of the 80s of the twentieth century noted the focus on maximum satisfaction of the ever-growing needs of the population. What is interesting here is that they pay attention to the effectiveness that can satisfy the needs of the population to the maximum. But how can this be achieved? There is no clear answer.

It should also be noted that the economic literature does not pay much attention to the important indicator of financial resources, final financial resources or income (profit). Although the indicator of costs was occasionally voiced, and taking into account the activities of business entities - profit. The question arises: what are all these definitions in the subtext of efficiency for, if this category does not bring anything new, a new result. In addition, this indicator was only voiced from a positive point of view in government documents, programs. So what if we could not implement it as a general indicator that could benefit an economic entity. Only some indicators involved in determining efficiency, for example, profit, had a general meaning, i.e. with the help of profitability, preferential conditions were created within the framework of tax payments. That is, the lower the relative value of profitability, then they were partially or completely exempted from paying taxes on profit or other mandatory payments. However, efficiency is not determined by such criteria. We only limited ourselves to voicing the concept of efficiency. This continues to this day. In our opinion, efficiency should have a therapeutic nature. It should not only be characterized by relative indicators, but also create additional stimulating conditions. Often, in certain

periods, we adequately matched high profit growth to the efficiency indicator. In these certain periods, stimulating mechanisms for the activities of enterprises were in effect. But now they are gone.

Let us consider the approaches of the authors to the definition of the category "efficiency", characteristic of the transitional period of the economy. In fairness, it should be noted that during the transitional period this issue, considered in the context of trade enterprises, including public catering, in one aspect or another were devoted to the works of such economists as: B.A. Raizberg, L.Sh. Lazovsky, P.A. Vatnik, R.A. Maksimenko, N.N. Ushakova, D.M. Rosenberg, Yu.L. Alexandrov, N.N. Tereshchenko and others.

B.A. Raizberg defines efficiency as a relative effect, the effectiveness of a process [17]. L.Sh. Lozovsky also characterizes efficiency as an economic category that characterizes the effectiveness of production by relating the result to the costs that ensured its achievement [11].

As follows from these definitions, one author takes as the basis of efficiency "... process", and the other "... production". Although they consider this indicator to be relative.

A number of economists argue that efficiency is characterized as the relationship between the number of sources for production (labor, raw materials, etc.) used by the enterprise and the number of goods produced using these sources, therefore, in this case the category "efficiency" is a relative indicator [16]. P.A. Vatnik defines efficiency as the relationship between the costs of rare factors and the output of goods and services [20].

A number of economists, namely: E.N. Khodjaev, T.A. Sattarov and others, believe that efficiency as an economic category reflects economic relations associated with improving the use of production resources and reducing total costs in the broad sense of the word to achieve the greatest results [8]. The approach to defining the category of "efficiency" by a group of authors represented by Yu.L. Alexandrov, N.N. Tereshchenko is slightly different, in which the authors generalize all types of resources aimed at achieving the best national economic results [1].

In his work, economist D.M. Rosenberg speaks of efficiency as productivity, performance, specifying the method for obtaining the value of the indicator "efficiency", similar to previous authors, which notes the similarity of this definition with the definitions presented in dictionaries. Rosenberg is the only one among the approaches considered to the definition of the category "efficiency" who compares it with performance and productivity, which, in our opinion, is somewhat incorrect, since these concepts are only a component part of the category "efficiency" [18].

E.F. Borisov notes that efficiency is the ratio between the obtained production results (products and services), on the one hand, and the costs of labor and means of production, on the other. For entrepreneurs, economic efficiency is determined by the ratio of the profit received (enterprise income) to the amount of advanced or fixed and working capital [3].

Based on the results of the analysis of economic literature of the transition economy period, i.e. the 1990s, a number of conclusions can be made regarding approaches to defining the category of "efficiency". Firstly, during this period, efficiency issues were considered broadly, but the depth of research in this category was insufficient, namely, efficiency issues were considered one-sidedly or narrowly. In our opinion, this was due, on the one hand, to the insufficiently formed conceptual apparatus, and on the other hand, to the fact that during the transition economy, socially significant aspects of the category of "efficiency" were lost. Consequently, the identified weaknesses in approaches to defining the category of "efficiency" even now do not allow us to objectively formulate a definition of efficiency characteristic of the analyzed period.

During the period of market economy, efficiency issues were given much attention and a significant number of works by Russian economists were published. It was considered in educational literature, and was also covered in periodicals and scientific publications. At present, efficiency issues continue to be

studied by such authors as N.V. Parushina, R.M. Nureyev, B.A. Raizberg, A. Tyapukhin, E. Fedulova, S.N. Lebedeva, N.A. Kazinachikova, A.V. Gavrikov, A. Shafronov, V.A. Chernov and other researchers. Each of the definitions of an individual economist is unique and specific in its own way, but often does not fully reveal the essence of this category.

Also, the system of indicators taken into account when calculating efficiency with subsequent assessment of the financial condition of the enterprise allows for its analysis exclusively in a comprehensive manner, without taking into account various types of activities and requests of individual categories taken into account when calculating efficiency. Therefore, the efficiency indicator is often calculated either only by the management personnel of enterprises in order to develop tactics and strategy for doing business, or to resolve financial issues in order to attract investors and creditors. The system of indicators included in the calculation of efficiency, calculated on the basis of the current procedure, is currently presented in economic literature in a variety of ways.

The methods of calculating the efficiency indicator proposed by scientists also do not take into account the cash flow at enterprises in three areas of activity: current, innovation-investment and financial, and do not subdivide the indicators for each area separately, considering the financial state based on the movement of capital and as a whole. At the same time, the allocation of independent areas of efficiency by economic spheres and the justification for the need to form a system of indicators taken into account when calculating efficiency in relation to a specific economic sphere should be uniform.

A number of authors in their works paid attention only to the quantitative features of efficiency, for example, in the works of N.V. Parushina, R.M. Nureyev, B.A. Raizberg, A. Tyapukhin. In their works, efficiency is characterized as the ratio of the achieved economic effect and various types of costs received in achieving this effect. In the sources indicated, the definition of "efficiency" means only its economic and mathematical content (calculation method), which in turn does not fully reveal the meaning of this category and requires further terminological analysis.

Most economists distinguish efficiency as a resulting indicator. Thus, according to B.A. Raizberg, A. Tyapukhin and N. Boldyrev, "efficiency" is a relative resulting indicator [17]. The latter note that efficiency is "... an indicator characterizing the positive dynamics of the development of an economic entity" [21]. E. Fedulova, defining efficiency, speaks of it as a complex socio-economic category, reflecting, first of all, the effectiveness of the use of labor embodied in the means of production and the productive force of living labor [23]. This approach to defining efficiency, in our opinion, characterizes it as an abstract category, which is also not convincing by definition.

G.S. Vechkanov, G.R. Vechkanova, when defining the category of efficiency, in addition to mentioning the ratio of results and costs, explain the condition for achieving it, namely, "... when production resources are distributed in such a way that their use ensures the maximum possible total net gain" [4]. That is, they define it as the total net gain.

A number of economists: S.N. Lebedeva, N.A. Kazinachikova, A.V. Gavrikov speak about efficiency as the ratio of the results of economic activity to the costs of resources that are necessary to carry out this activity [10]. V.A. Chernov understands efficiency as the degree of achieving the best results with the least costs [25], and A. Shafronov believes that one should understand not the ratio of results and costs (as is currently accepted), but the degree of use of the production potential of enterprises [26].

Thus, all definitions of the efficiency category are justified in their own way and each of them considers their definition to be indisputable and correct.

We respect the opinion of each scientist, because each approach to defining the category of efficiency is the result of research, laid down by a large scientific work. But, despite this, in terms of their effectiveness, how comparable can they be? Effectiveness should be manifested both from the qualitative and quantitative side. Taking this into account, we approached the definition of efficiency from a different

angle. Because the study has already encountered a completely new approach, in particular, that this category reflects not only the effectiveness, but also the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the activities of enterprises, and also determines the ratio of results to costs. When considering this category, it is imperative to also take into account not only economic aspects that are favorable for the intensification and increase in productivity of enterprises, but also social ones, contributing to the assessment of the degree of satisfaction of demand, the needs of the population, as well as obtaining socially significant results through achieving an economic effect.

Based on the work done, in our opinion, efficiency can be defined as a socio-economic result, characterized by quantitative and qualitative indicators in relative values, obtained in the implementation of innovative activities through the relationship of the result of this activity with the maximum effort of using resources in the broad sense of the word.

It follows that the activity of an economic entity will be considered most effective with the multidirectional development of the factors that determine it. In this case, the result should tend to the maximum (\uparrow), and efforts, time and resources - to the minimum (\downarrow).

Therefore, the concretized concept of "efficiency" should reflect not only economic but also social aspects of efficiency. The latter should specify that the assessment of efficiency is possible only with the help of a system of indicators specially developed and adapted to a specific type of activity and including both quantitative and qualitative indicators, which will allow for a more accurate and high-quality diagnostics of efficiency.

References:

1. Alexandrov Yu.L. Economics of a trading enterprise: textbook . individual / Yu.L.Aleksandrov, N.N.Tereshchenko, I.V.Petruchenya / Krasnoyarsk state university. - Krasnoyarsk, 1997.- 220 p .
2. Large Economic Dictionary / Ed. by A.N.Azriliyan. - M.: Institute of New Economics, 2008. - 1472 p.
3. Borisov E.F. Economics: reference book / E.F. Borisov. - 2nd ed. - M.: Finance and Statistics, 1998. - 400 p .
4. Vechkanov G.S. Modern economic encyclopedia / G.S.Vechkanov, G.R.Vechkanova. - St. Petersburg: Lan, 2002. - 880 p .
5. Zadorozhny V.K. What does the economics of trade teach? / V.K. Zadorozhny. - Kiev: Vishcha shkola, 1975. - 32 p .
6. Zadorozhny V.K. Efficiency of Soviet trade / V.K.Zadorozhny. - M.: Knowledge, 1974. - 64 p .
7. Lebedeva S.N. Economics of a trading enterprise: textbook . n individual / S.N.Lebedeva, N.A.Kazinachikova, A.V.Gavrikov. - Minsk: New edition, 2001. - 240 p .
8. Lozovsky L.Sh. Dictionary of Economics and Law / L.Sh.Lozovsky, B.A.Raizberg. - M.: Omega, 1999.- 608 p .
9. Economic dictionary. - M.: FIS, 1999.
10. Akhrorov G. Enterprise finance. - T., 2022.
11. Nureyev R.M. Microeconomics course: textbook . for universities / R.M.Nureyev. - 2nd ed. - M.: Norma, 2007. - 567 p.
12. Parushina N.V. Analysis of efficiency and intensification in trade / N.V. Parushina, V.E. Gubin, O.V. Gubina // Accounting and analysis of trade activities. - 2009. - No. 2. - P. 12-15.

13. Pass K. Large explanatory dictionary of business / K. Pass, B. Laws, E. Pendleton, L. Chadwick. - M.: Veche, AST, 1998. - 688 p .
14. Raizberg B.A. Modern economic dictionary / B.A. Raizberg, L.Sh. Lozovsky, E.B. Starodubtseva. - 5th ed. add. and reab. - M.: INFRA-M, 2007. - 495 p.
15. Rosenberg D.M. Business and Management: Terminological Dictionary / D.M. Rosenberg. - M.: INFRA-M, 1997. - 464 p.
16. Rummyantseva E.E. New Economic Encyclopedia / E.E.Rummyantseva. - 3rd ed. - M.: INFRA-M, 2008. - 826 p .
17. Dictionary of Economics / translated from English; edited by P.A.Vatnik. - St. Petersburg: Economic School, 1998. - 752 p .
18. Tyapukhin A. Evaluation of the effectiveness of economic systems and subsystems of the enterprise / A. Tyapukhin, N. Boldyreva // Resources, information, supply, competition. - 2006. - No. 1. - P. 4-11.
19. Fedulova E. The essence of economic efficiency of production / E. Fedulova // Entrepreneurship. - 2006. - No. 1. - P. 95-101.
20. Chaplina A.N. Competitiveness as an integral indicator of enterprise efficiency / A.N. Chaplina, I.A. Voitsekhovskaya // Problems of Theory and Practice of Management. - 2006. - No. 3. - P. 108-112.
21. Chernov V.A. Economic analysis: trade, public catering, tourism business: textbook . n special for universities / V.A.Chernov; edited by M.I.Bakanov. - M.: UNITY-DANA, 2003. - 686 p.
22. Shafronov A. New approach to production efficiency / A. Shafronov // Economist. - 2003. - No. 4. - P. 82-87.
23. Economic and Mathematical Encyclopedic Dictionary / edited by V.I. Danilov-Danilyan. - M.: Exam, 2003. - 688.